

NONLINEAR COLLAPSE OF THIN-WALLED COMPOSITE
CYLINDERS UNDER FLEXURAL LOADING

Keith T. Kedward

General Dynamics Convair Division
San Diego, California

SUMMARY

Following a review of the mechanics of nonlinear behavior of long thin-walled cylinders in bending, expressions are developed for laminated composite and orthotropic shell constructions. The interaction between local buckling and nonlinear effects is also discussed and presented graphically. Numerical solutions derived by an alternate approach involving the application of nonlinear shell analysis computer codes are presented and compared to the results from the closed-form expressions.

INTRODUCTION

The stability of isotropic circular cylindrical shells subjected to pure bending loads has been discussed in a number of publications, notably by Seide and Weingarten (1). Invariably, it is proven that bifurcation (short wave) buckling occurs when the maximum axial compressive stress approximates that required to cause similar failure in a uniformly compressed cylinder; in the case of isotropic cylinders the pertinent expression is $\sigma_{cr} = 0.606 Et/a$. The corresponding expression for orthotropic cylinders is $\sigma_{cr} = \sqrt{\frac{E_x E_y}{3(1-\nu_{xy}\nu_{yx})}} \frac{t}{a} \Phi$ where Φ is the lesser of 1 and $\sqrt{\frac{2G_{xy}(1-\nu_{xy}\nu_{yx})}{\sqrt{E_x E_y}}}$

However, the treatment invoked to obtain the above simple expressions presupposes that the cylinder is relatively short; typically the length and diametral dimensions are similar.

For much longer cylinders, the application of such expressions yield grossly inaccurate and unconservative predictions. The reason is associated with extreme finite distortion (flattening) of the cylinder cross-section, i.e. the prebuckling deformation (see Figure 1). The phenomenon can be appreciated qualitatively by observing the contribution of the inwardly-directed components of the axial stress resultants in conjunction with the Poisson-type contraction and expansion of the semicircular circumference on the tension and compression side of the neutral plane, respectively. As a result of the cross-section flattening, the flexural stiffness is degraded with increasing load until collapse occurs.

FIGURE 1.

CROSS-SECTIONAL DEFORMATION PREDICTED BY NUMERICAL ANALYSIS

Consequences of the shape change are an increase in maximum compressive stress, a change in the axial stress distribution, and a reduction in the bifurcation buckling stress by virtue of the increase in the circumferential radius of curvature at the critical location. Substantial bending stresses may also develop in the transverse direction which are potentially damaging to certain types of composite laminates.

For the case of isotropic cylinders, Brazier (2) developed a closed-form expression for the nonlinear collapse moment based on infinitely long cylinders. From this expression, it is implicit that the maximum compressive stress at incipient collapse is given by $\sigma_{cr} = 0.33 Et/a$ which is seen to be considerably lower than that representing classical bifurcation buckling failure.

Expressions for orthotropic and laminated composite shells which are equivalent to the expressions deduced by Brazier for isotropic shells are developed below. The influence of the nonlinear prebuckling deformation on the predicted bifurcation buckling stress level is then discussed and an approximate technique for determining the maximum load carrying capability of a composite tube is proposed.

THEORETICAL DISCUSSION

In Brazier's (2) original formulation of the nonlinear behavior of infinitely long isotropic shells, it was assumed that radial displacements are small compared to shell radius 'a' and that a condition of inextensibility prevails in the circumferential direction. By eliminating the second-order terms in displacement components (v and w), Brazier then derived the sixth-order Euler equation from which the solution was readily obtained. In a later, more rigorous approach, Reissner (3) obtained approximate solutions to the nonlinear differential equations developed in the form of power expansions. On that occasion, Reissner concluded, by considering only three terms in the expansion, that Brazier's expression for critical moment was in error by approximately ten percent. However, in a subsequent treatment (4), Reissner revised his assessment based on the computation of additional terms in the expansion. Essentially, it was realized that consideration of three or four terms in the expansion can produce results which are further from the correct results than the value based on only two terms. As a consequence, it was demonstrated that the approximate approach of Brazier provides results of acceptable accuracy. On the basis of this knowledge, a similar treatment to that of Brazier is utilized below to obtain results for composite shells.

The tendency for a thin-walled circular cylinder, of any wall material, to develop an ovalized cross-section when uniformly flexed has been discussed in physical terms. The corresponding theoretical background is now developed along lines similar to those adopted by Brazier (2) for isotropic cylinders.

It is first important to review the assumptions which must be invoked to develop manageable theoretical expressions:

- (i) The shell is assumed to be infinitely long such that the deformation of cross-sections are unaffected by end boundary conditions. This implies that the curvature of the cylinder axis is independent of the axial coordinate.
- (ii) Deformation of the shell cross-section with respect to the shell circumference is inextensional. It follows that the relationship $w = \frac{\partial v}{\partial \theta}$ may be introduced.
- (iii) Displacement components v (tangential to shell circumference) and w (radial) are always small compared to the radius of the shell.

The implications of the above assumptions in general and their effect on laminated composite shell in particular will be discussed later.

Following Brazier (Ref. 1), we first consider the small displacement solution for the flexure state, i.e.:

$$w_0 = \frac{1}{2} \nu_{xy} \frac{a^2}{\rho} \cos \theta$$

$$v_0 = -\frac{1}{2} \nu_{xy} \frac{a^2}{\rho} \sin \theta \quad (1)$$

where ν_{xy} is the Poisson's ratio characterizing the circumferential (y) strain created by an axial (x) stress.

A further set of displacements v_1, w_1 develop when the tube conforms, under finite displacements, to a position of minimum strain energy, such that:

$$w = w_1 + w_0$$

$$v = v_1 + v_0 \quad (2)$$

where w, v are total displacements.

Introducing the inextensibility condition (assumption (ii) above), we may relate:

$$w_1 = \frac{dv_1}{d\theta} \quad (3)$$

Now the ovalization of the cross-section can be defined mathematically by the change of curvature with respect to θ :

$$\text{i.e., } \chi_\theta = \frac{1}{a^2} \left(w_1 + \frac{d^2 w_1}{d\theta^2} \right) = \frac{1}{a^2} \left(\frac{dv_1}{d\theta} + \frac{d^3 v_1}{d\theta^3} \right) \quad (4)$$

Equation (4) can also be written:

$$\chi_\theta = \frac{1}{a^2} \left(\frac{dv}{d\theta} + \frac{d^3 v}{d\theta^3} \right) \quad (4a)$$

by introducing equation (1) and (2) into (4).

The resultant longitudinal strain at any circumferential location θ can be related to the distance 'd' from the central surface:

$$\text{that is . . . } d = (a - w) \cos \theta - v \sin \theta \quad (5)$$

From the above equations we may now formulate an expression for the total strain energy per unit length of tube which is made up of:

(a) The strain energy due to flexure of the cross-section given by . . .

$$U_a = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^{2\pi} M \chi_\theta a d\theta = \frac{1}{2} D_{22} \int_0^{2\pi} \chi_\theta^2 a d\theta \quad (6)$$

(b) The strain energy due to extensional deformation along the shell axis . . .

$$U_b = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^{2\pi} \sigma_x \epsilon_x a t d\theta \quad (7)$$

Hence we derive an expression for the total strain energy incorporating the appropriate equations for χ_θ and ϵ_x , the latter being deduced from equation (5):

$$U = U_a + U_b = \frac{1}{2} D_{22} \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{1}{a^4} \left(\frac{d^3 v}{d\theta^3} + \frac{dv}{d\theta} \right)^2 a d\theta \quad (8)$$

$$+ \frac{1}{2} E_x \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{a^2 t}{\rho^2} \left\{ \left[a^2 - 2a \left(\frac{dv}{d\theta} + \nu_{xy} \frac{a^2}{\rho} \cos \theta \right) \right] \cos^2 \theta - a v \sin 2\theta \right\} d\theta$$

neglecting terms which involve products of small quantities.

For the strain energy to be a minimum, it is well known, from the Calculus of variations, that Euler's equation must be satisfied:

$$\frac{d^6 v}{d\theta^6} + \frac{2 d^4 v}{d\theta^4} + \frac{d^2 v}{d\theta^2} = \frac{3}{2} \frac{a^5}{\rho^2} \frac{E_x}{D_{22}} \sin 2\theta \quad (9)$$

The standard solution to this equation yields:

$$v = \frac{a^5}{24} \frac{t}{\rho^2} \frac{E_x}{D_{22}} \sin 2\theta \quad (10)$$

$$\text{It follows that: } w = \frac{a^5}{12} \cdot \frac{t}{\rho^2} \frac{E_x}{D_{22}} \cdot \cos 2\theta + \nu_{xy} \frac{a^2}{\rho} \cos \theta \quad (11)$$

Substituting (10) and (11) into (8) gives

$$U = \frac{1}{2} D_{22} \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{1}{a^4} \left[\frac{a^5}{4} \cdot \frac{t}{\rho^2} \cdot \frac{E_x}{D_{22}} \right]^2 \cos^2 2\theta \cdot a d\theta + \frac{1}{2} E_x \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{a^2 t}{\rho^2} \left\{ \left[a^2 - 2a \frac{a^5}{24} \cdot \frac{t}{\rho^2} \cdot \frac{E_x}{D_{22}} \cos 2\theta \right. \right.$$

$$\left. \left. + \nu_{xy} \frac{a^2}{\rho} \cos \theta \right] \cos^2 \theta - a \left[\frac{a^5}{24} \cdot \frac{t}{\rho^2} \cdot \frac{E_x}{D_{22}} \right] \sin^2 2\theta \right\} d\theta \quad (12)$$

Integrating equation (12) and introducing $M = dU/d(1/\rho) = 0$ for maximum

then:

$$\frac{1}{\rho^2} = \frac{8}{3} \frac{D_{22}}{a^4 t E_x} \quad (13)$$

and

$$M = E_x \cdot \pi a^3 t \frac{1}{\rho} \left[1 - \frac{1}{8} a^2 t \frac{E_x}{D_{22}} \frac{1}{\rho^2} \right] \quad (14)$$

Therefore:

$$M_{\text{crit}} = \frac{2}{3} E_x \cdot \pi a^3 t \cdot \frac{2\sqrt{2}}{\sqrt{3}} \frac{1}{a} \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\frac{D_{22}}{E_x t}}$$

$$M_{\text{crit}} = \frac{4\sqrt{2}}{3\sqrt{3}} \cdot E_x \pi a t \sqrt{\frac{D_{22}}{E_x t}} \quad (15)$$

It is also convenient to express the bending moment applied to the shell in terms of the curvature, thus characterizing the non-linear nature of the load-displacement curve. For this purpose the initial second moment of area of the shell cross-section will be used, i.e., $I = \pi a^3 t$.

Thus; from equation (14)

$$\frac{M}{E_x I} = \frac{1}{\rho} \left[1 - \frac{1}{8} \frac{a^4}{\rho^2} \cdot \frac{E_x t}{D_{22}} \right] \quad (16)$$

Here, the second term in parentheses represents the non-linear phenomenon developing as the square of the curvature of the tube axis.

The reduction in vertical diameter ' Δ ' which contributes the non-linear effect can be expressed in terms of equation (11) using w_0 and w_π as the radial displacements at $\theta = 0$ and $\theta = \pi$, respectively.

Thus,

$$\Delta = w_0 + w_\pi = \frac{a^5}{6} \cdot \frac{E_x t}{D_{22}} \cdot \frac{1}{\rho^2}$$

$$\text{alternatively: } \frac{\Delta}{2a} = \frac{a^4}{12 \rho^2} \cdot \frac{E_x t}{D_{22}} \quad (17)$$

Finally we may obtain expressions for the special case of an orthotropic shell of axial stiffness E_x , circumferential stiffness E_y , by reducing expressions (15), (16) and (17) as follows:

$$M_{\text{crit}} = \frac{2\sqrt{2}}{9} \frac{E_x \pi a t^2}{\sqrt{(1 - \nu_{xy} \nu_{yx})}} \sqrt{\frac{E_y}{E_x}} \quad (15A)$$

$$\frac{M}{E_x I_x} = \frac{1}{\rho} \left[1 - \frac{3}{2} \frac{a^4}{\rho^2 t^2} \frac{E_x}{E_y} (1 - \nu_{xy} \nu_{yx}) \right] \quad (16A)$$

$$\frac{\Delta}{2a} = \frac{a^4}{\rho^2 t^2} (1 - \nu_{xy} \nu_{yx}) \frac{E_x}{E_y} \quad (17A)$$

Further reduction to the isotropic case, using $E_x = E_y = E$, yields the well known relationships originally published by Brazier (2).

Figure 2 illustrates the degree of nonlinearity predicted by the equations (16) and (17) derived above.

FIGURE 2.

NON-LINEAR DISPLACEMENT CHARACTERISTICS OF LONG CYLINDERS IN PURE BENDING.

At this juncture it is appropriate to re-examine the assumptions introduced to facilitate the above derivation. The first assumption of infinite length is obviously applicable only to situations wherein a substantial length of the shell distorts in a prismatic manner. End boundary conditions which usually constrain the end cross-sections to remain circular can play an important role in the general stability characteristics of a long shell. Restricting the treatment to isotropic wall materials, Aksel'rad (6), using an approximate asymptotic solution procedure, derived an expression (equation 5.1) which classifies the fully established Brazier effect. Aksel'rad's expression may be approximated to a more convenient form:

$$\frac{L}{a} \geq 2.5 \sqrt{\frac{a}{t}} \quad (18)$$

which defines the long shell nonlinear collapse regime. Figure 3 illustrates the form of the transition from short to long shell collapse behavior as predicted by Aksel'rad for isotropic materials.

FIGURE 3.

COLLAPSE STRESS FOR THIN-WALLED CYLINDERS IN PURE BENDING

With regard to the second assumption involving inextensibility of the finite system of displacements v_1 and w_1 , it is probable that certain composite laminate constructions may deviate significantly from this condition. Specifically a low transverse stiffness and a very large Poisson's ratio, both of which are feasible with most advanced composite systems, may create a condition for which the energy absorbed by extensional displacement may not be large compared to the transverse bending strain energy. A more rigorous treatment, or an acceptable numerical solution, will be required before a quantitative assessment of the validity of the inextensibility assumption can be obtained.

Finally, the third assumption postulates that the v, w displacement components are always small compared to the radius of the shell. The assumption allows products of the displacement components to be ignored thereby simplifying the treatment. However, subsequent work by Reissner (3,4), adopting more rigorous treatments, has effectively substantiated the validity of the assumption. Since it can be seen from above equations (13) and (17), that the cross-sectional distortion at collapse is the same for all material constructions, it appears reasonable to retain Brazier's assumption for the formulation of the composite shell equations. The reduction in vertical diameter Δ can be written:

$$\Delta = \frac{2}{9} \times (2a) \tag{19}$$

(2a) being the initial shell diameter.

Up to this point the discussion has been confined to the nonlinear deformation of the thin-walled shell in flexure. Actually this geometric nonlinearity merely describes the prebuckling state of the shell and bifurcation (short wave) buckling from this state may occur prior to nonlinear collapse. This possibility was also considered by Aksel'rad (6) who assumed an equivalent cylinder approach in which

the instantaneous radius of curvature at the location of maximum compressive stress was utilized in determining the bifurcation failure level. This approximate though reasonable approach can best be appreciated by illustrating the important parameter variations in graphical form. Figure 4 indicates the changes in curvature, compressive stress, and buckling stress which develop due to nonlinear influences. Quantitatively it can be shown, using equations (4) and (10), that the pertinent radius of curvature at the point of nonlinear collapse has increased to 1.5 times the initial radius of the shell cross section.

FIGURE 4.

APPROXIMATE METHOD OF ESTIMATING INTERACTION OF LOCAL & GENERAL INSTABILITY

ILLUSTRATIVE EXAMPLES

Using the expressions derived above it is informative to study numerical results for certain types of laminate. It will be assumed that the designer wishes to provide a 12 in. diameter, long tubular shell of high flexural stiffness and low weight. A wall thickness of 0.040 in. will be used. To this end he decides to use an ultra-high modulus graphite fiber/epoxy matrix system. Candidate laminates are

Type A: Unidirectional layup, 8 layers at 0° angle.

Type B: Cross-ply arrangement, $[0_2, \pm 45]_S$

Type C: Cross-ply arrangement, $[\pm 45, 0_2]_S$

Layer properties were determined by coupon testing as follows:

$$E_L = 40.7 \times 10^6 \text{ lb/in}^2$$

$$G_{LT} = 0.95 \times 10^6 \text{ lbf/in}^2$$

$$E_T = 0.93 \times 10^6 \text{ lb/in}^2$$

$$\nu_{LT} = 0.30$$

Ply thickness = 0.005 in.

In general an all-unidirectional design will be unacceptable due to the extremely low transverse strength and general fragility of the structure in a thin-shell form.

Although the stress levels which will be imposed by design loading conditions are of

no serious concern the designer is aware of potential stability problems. From the above discussion it is clear that he should consider the general instability level of the long tube structure rather than the local condition. Use of equation (15) for the cross-ply laminates (Types B and C) and equation (15a) for the unidirectional (Type A) laminates is necessary.

A summary of the inputs and results for each laminate type is given in Table 1. The poor stability performance of the unidirectional cylinder (laminate Type A) was anticipated as was the similarly poor performance of the Type B laminate. Placing the 45° layers nearest the surface of the cylinder markedly increases the transverse flexural rigidity (D_{22}) and the critical bending moment is increased dramatically as a consequence.

Table 1. Properties and Critical Bending Moments for a Selection of Laminates

Type	Lamination Sequence	Axial Stiffness ($E_x/10^6$) (lb/in ²)	Poisson's Ratio (ν_{xy})	Transverse Flexural Rigidity (D_{22}) (lb-in ²)	Collapse Moment (M_{crit}) (lb-in)
A	[0 ₈]	40.7	0.30	4.97	58,400
B	[0 ₂ , ±45 _s]	22.2	0.795	12.03	67,100
C	[±45, 0 ₂] _s	22.2	0.795	54.38	142,600

It is also noteworthy that a pseudoisotropic laminate of the same material and thickness will exhibit still higher collapse moments, at the expense of axial stiffness, by virtue of further enhancement of flexural rigidity. Also important is the error associated with use of Brazier's isotropic equation for pseudoisotropic laminates. This approach will yield predicted collapse moments which may be significantly different from the more correct values from equation (15).

Of course an alternate practical solution to the low flexural stability of long tubular shells is the addition of stiffening rings or diaphragms at appropriate locations. This may not be practicable or economical in certain applications, however, and thought must be given to establishing an 'optimum' stacking sequence. The expressions developed above should assist the designer in this regard.

NUMERICAL SOLUTIONS

The above analytical solution is clearly confined to ideal situations and merely provides bounds to the majority of practical engineering problems. Consequently, the structural analyst must resort to comprehensive numerical methods often by the application of available computer codes. In these circumstances, he (she) is invariably faced with the prospect of high analysis costs and prudent selection of

suitable computer programs is vitally important.

Two candidate computer codes were considered for the analysis of the long shell flexure problem. The first, a general purpose nonlinear finite element code known as MARC-CDC (7), was found unacceptable after considering two alternate structural models. Numerical problems associated with the use of a curved pipe element were experienced when a very large radius was specified in an attempt to represent the initially straight shell configuration. Use of two types of doubly-curved shell elements to represent a quarter-shell portion, taking advantage of structural symmetry, was attempted (see Figure 5). In both cases a satisfactory solution to the nonlinear problem could not be achieved using the mesh subdivision illustrated in this figure.

FIGURE 5.

MATHEMATICAL, QUARTER-CYLINDER MODEL SHOWING MESH SUBDIVISION SELECTED FOR NUMERICAL ANALYSIS USING STAGS

The high analysis costs associated with the above idealization precluded further consideration of analyses based on a more refined element subdivision.

A second computer code, STAGS (8), based on a finite difference energy formulation, and particularly suited to nonlinear and bifurcation collapse analysis of shell structures, was selected. Previous application of this code to similar problems had produced satisfactory results as described by Stephens, Starnes & Almroth (5).

Using various versions of this computer code, and based on the same mesh subdivision as that used for the MARC-CDC finite element analysis (Figure 5), a number of solutions were obtained with varying degrees of success. Use of the A-version of STAGS was shown to overestimate structural stiffness in the large displacement regime. It was subsequently discovered (9) that certain omissions from the strain-displacement relations, notably the rotation term, $(\partial u/\partial y)^2$, becomes relatively large in the flexure of very long tubes. A more satisfactory solution was achieved by use of the C-version although poor convergence was experienced due to the large rigid body displacements developed in the long shell. All ill-conditioning was observed in the form of non-zero equilibrium forces which were checked at specific locations

during nonlinear load increments. In the earlier work of Stephens et. al. (5), the tube lengths studied were insufficiently long to encounter the severe problems experienced in the present author's studies.

The most satisfactory solution obtained is included as data points on Figure 2 where comparison with the approximate solution developed above can be drawn.

The STAGS developers (9) have subsequently improved the capability for the analysis of problems involving such extreme rigid body displacements and a new version of the code, the C1 version, will be made available shortly. Nevertheless, the writer strongly recommends a parallel investigation, to that reported herein, be made before committing oneself to extensive use of the code on similar problems.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

The mechanics of deformation and stability of long cylindrical shells in general have been described, and the peculiar effects presented by laminated composite shells in particular discussed. Equations, developed specifically for thin-walled composite shells, were presented with indications of the effect of approximations introduced by the three principal assumptions of Brazier theory. These equations should prove useful for design calculations pertaining to long composite tubes which experience flexural loading. In the event that a more definitive analysis is required, use of a suitable computer code, such as the STAGS-C program considered herein, is recommended. For the complex loading and boundary conditions encountered in most practical design problems, the only tractable approach is by use of a numerical method. However, one is cautioned that an acceptable numerical solution to a shell structure experiencing such a high degree of nonlinearity, and rigid body displacements, has yet to be obtained.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The several stimulating discussions with Bo Almroth, Frank Brogan, and co-workers at Lockheed Missiles and Space Company in Palo Alto, California, are gratefully acknowledged. The author appreciates the advice offered during attempts to obtain acceptable numerical solutions to the frustrating long shell problem.

The permission and assistance given by General Dynamics Convair Division in connection with the preparation and presentation of this paper is also acknowledged with gratitude.

REFERENCES

1. P. Seide & V. E. Weingarten, "On the Buckling of Circular Cylindrical Shells Under Pure Bending," *J. Appl. Mech.*, 28, 1, 1.112, 1961.
2. L. G. Brazier, "On the Flexure of Thin Cylindrical Shells and Other 'Thin' Sections," *Proc. Roy. Soc., Series A*, CXVI, p. 104, 1927.
3. E. Reissner, "On Finite Bending of Pressurized Tubes," *J. Appl. Mech.*, 26, p. 386, 1959.
4. E. Reissner & H. J. Weinitschke, "Finite Pure Bending of Circular Cylindrical Tubes," *Quart. Appl. Math.*, XX, 4, p. 305, January 1963.
5. W. B. Stephens, J. H. Starnes, Jr., & B. O. Almroth, "Collapse of Long Cylindrical Shells under Combined Bending and Pressure Loads," *AIAA Paper No. 74-407*, 1974.
6. E. L. Aksel'rad, "Refinement of the Upper Critical Loading of Pipe Bending Taking Account of the Geometrical Nonlinearity," (In Russian), *Izvestia, Akademiia Nauk, SSSR, Otdelenie Tekhnicheskikh Nauk, Mekhanika*, No. 4, p. 123, 1965.
7. B. O. Almroth, F. A. Brogan & G. M. Stanley, "Structural Analysis of General Shells," Vol. III, Users Instructions for STAGS-C, LMSC D502277, Lockheed Missiles & Space Company, Inc., Palo Alto, December 1975.
8. B. O. Almroth & F. A. Brogan, Lockheed Missiles & Space Co., Inc., Private Communication, May 1976.
9. MARC-CDC, "Nonlinear Finite Element Analysis Program," User Information Manual, Vol. 1, Control Data Corp., 1975.